

Studies on Some Complexes of Blue Perchromate

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In continuation of our previous work¹⁻⁶ on blue perchromate, we have now studied the compounds formed during its reaction with organic nitrogenous compounds.

Analytical and chemical investigation of such compounds is important as it can furnish information regarding the composition of blue perchromate.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals were of A.R. Grade. Procedure regarding preparation of blue perchromate was similar to that described earlier (loc. cit). Wiede's method was used for preparing the complexes and concentrations of various nitrogenous compounds were as follows :

1. Salicyldoxime 5% ethereal solution.
2. Diphenylamine 5% ethereal solution.
3. α -naphthylamine saturated alcoholic solution.
4. Aluminon saturated alcoholic solution.
5. Diphenyl benzidine saturated ethereal solution.

50 ml. of cold organic base solution was added drop by drop to cold ethereal blue perchromate (50 ml). The compound formed as precipitate was filtered and washed with solvent used for base. The compounds were then dried.

Estimation of Chromium : Chromium was estimated gravimetrically as Cr_2O_3 .

Estimation of Nitrogen and Carbon : Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method, and carbon by usual combustion method. Molecular weights of the compounds could not be determined by cryoscopic method due to insoluble nature of compounds.

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TABLE I
Analytical data

Name of complex	Appearance and colour	Proposed formula	Cr		N		C	
			Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
Salicyl doxime	Amorphous dark brown	R Cr O ₅ or R ₂ Cr ₂ O ₁₀	19.33	20.80	5.20	5.00	31.22	31.00
Diphenylamine	Amorphous black	R ₃ Cr ₁ O ₁₀	7.21	7.60	5.84	5.40	60.08	62.12
α -naphthylamine	Amorphous dark violet	R ₂ Cr ₂ O ₅ or R ₄ Cr ₄ O ₁₀	22.12	21.90	5.95	5.78	51.06	51.72
Aluminon	Amorphous reddish pink	R Cr ₂ O ₂₀	13.08	12.50	Nil	Nil	33.20	31.84
Diphenyl benzidine	Amorphous black	R Cr O ₅ or R ₂ Cr ₂ O ₁₀	11.11	10.90	5.98	Nil	61.53	61.00

Complexes dissolved in alkalis give chromate like solution. The solution was titrated iodometrically in the following two ways :

(a) 20 ml. of the solution was acidified with dilute (2*N*) sulphuric acid and titrated iodometrically against *N*/100 sodium thiosulphate solution using potassium iodide and starch solution as indicator.

(b) 20 ml. of the same solution was first treated with 2 ml. of 30% H₂O₂, boiled for about half an hour (to expel excess of H₂O₂), cooled, acidified and titrated against same thio-sulphate solution as above. Ratio for the oxidised/unoxidised, i.e., *b/a* titration values for different cases was found to be

Name of complex	Ratio oxidized/unoxidised i.e., <i>b/a</i>
1. Salicyldoxime	2 : 1
2. Diphenylamine	1 : 1
3. α -naphthylamine	1 : 1
4. Aluminon	2.5 : 1
5. Diphenyl benzidine	1 : 1

DISCUSSION

Analytical data given above suggest association of base molecule with blue perchromate. It corroborates the observation of previous workers⁷⁻¹².

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A perusal of the CrO_5 and $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ formulae for the blue perchromate shows that the association of base molecule is more feasible with $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_{10})_3$ formula. In CrO_5 , the only hexavalent chromium atom will perhaps not be able to associate the base molecule.

Absence of nitrogen in aluminon complex is probably due to the replacement of three NH_4^+ of aluminon by Cr^{+3} . Absence of nitrogen in diphenylbenzidine complex is however not clear.

Oxidation of trivalent chromium in alkaline medium by peroxide oxygen is known^{4,11}. The value of 1 : 1 for oxidized/unoxidized titration values for diphenylamine, diphenylbenzidine and α -naphthylamine complexes is thus as expected. In other cases the increase in titration values on oxidation is probably due to incomplete oxidation of trivalent chromium.

Financial assistance by U.G.C. to one of the authors (BSR) is gratefully acknowledged.

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Received October 21, 1970

